

VETERINARY SCIENCES

ROBUSTNESS AND SKELETAL STRENGTH INDEXES IN SHEPHERD DOGS

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Abstract

Shepherd dogs, along with hunting dogs, belong to the group of the oldest dogs. Shepherd dogs are characterized by a strong constitution, which means they have a strong skeletal structure.

Tornjak, officially known as the Bosnian-Herzegovinian-Croatian Shepherd Dog - Tornjak, originates from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina. The Sarplaninac has the official name Yugoslav Shepherd Dog – Sarplaninac, and its origins are in Serbia and North Macedonia. The Kangal is a Turkish shepherd dog. These three breeds of shepherd dogs are officially recognized by the International Cynological Federation (FCI). Akbash is a breed of shepherd dog in Turkey that has not yet been officially recognized by FCI.

To compare the body structure, or constitution, of four shepherd dog breeds – Tornjak, Akbash, Kangal, and Šarplaninac – we calculated and compared the skeletal strength index and index of robustness.

For both indexes, very low values of the coefficient of variation (CV) and standard deviation (SD) were determined. This clearly confirms that the observed populations of the four breeds of shepherd dogs are very homogeneous regarding the observed parameters. Differences among breeds, as well as between sexes within breeds, are insignificant.

Keywords: *Shepherd dogs, body structure, skeletal strength index and index of robustness.*

Introduction

Shepherd dogs, along with hunting dogs, belong to the group of the oldest dogs. Authors have written about the existence and use of such dogs, which are essentially guard dogs, since ancient times. Xenophon (431-354 BC) left a written record that there are two groups of dogs: guard dogs and hunting dogs (Tureen, 2024). Throughout all periods of civilization, as humans improved and advanced livestock farming, shepherd dogs were present and significantly helped in guarding flocks of sheep, goats, and other domestic animals.

Shepherd dogs are characterized by a strong constitution, which means they have a strong skeletal structure. According to the craniological classification by Jean Pierre Mégnin (1828-1905), shepherd dogs belong to the molossoid group.

Tornjak, officially known as the Bosnian-Herzegovinian-Croatian Shepherd Dog - Tornjak, originates from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina. The Sarplaninac has the official name Yugoslav Shepherd Dog – Sarplaninac, and its origins are in Serbia and North Macedonia. The Kangal is a Turkish shepherd dog. These three breeds of shepherd dogs are officially recognized by the International Cynological Federation (FCI). Akbash is a breed of shepherd dog in Turkey that has not yet been officially recognized by FCI.

In the available literature, there are no references that compare these indices in shepherd dogs, and thus, there is no data for comparing these indices in the four mentioned breeds of shepherd dogs. Yilmaz and Ertugrul (2012), studying the morphometric parameters of the Turkish shepherd dog Akbash, determined that the average height of males was 75.0+/-0.85 cm, and the average height at the withers of females was 74.4+/-0.78 cm. The chest circumference of males was 86.7+/-1.09 cm, and that of females was 86.2+/-1.23 cm. The average value of the pastern circumference for males was 13.2+/-0.20 cm, and for females, it was 13.3+/-0.15 cm.

Bijelić et al. (2013) in their analysis of the exterior of the Tornjak, stated that the average height at the withers of adult males was 69.20 cm, and the chest circumference was 89.10 cm. For females, the average height at the withers was 68.00 cm, and the chest circumference was 85.00 cm. Muhammedagić et al. (2009), studying the morphometric parameters of the Tornjak, reported that the average height at the withers of males is 66.78+/-0.50 cm, and for females, it is 63.13+/-0.43 cm. The average chest circumference of males was 85.40 cm and 80.29 cm for females.

Studying the exterior of the Sarabi shepherd dog in Iran, Urošević et al. (2023) found that the average height at the withers of males was 67.88 cm, the circumference of the pastern was 16.00 cm, and the

average chest circumference was 85.75 cm. The authors did not have the opportunity to study the morphometric parameters of females of this breed. Ograk et al. (2018) reported that the skeletal index of male Turkish Kangal shepherd dogs is 22.45. Urošević and Drobnjak (2011) stated that the average height at the withers in the population of the Yugoslav Shepherd Dog, the Šarplaninac, is 66.89 cm.

Daskiran (2007) states that the average height at the withers of male Kangals is 71.7 cm \pm 0.76 cm, and for females, it is 65.2 \pm 0.53 cm. The author notes that the average chest circumference of males is 86.1 \pm 1.81 cm, and for females, it is 78.8 \pm 0.95 cm. The pastern circumference of males was 14.6 \pm 0.23 cm and 12.9 \pm 0.16 cm for females. Urošević et al. (2012) reported that the average height at the withers of male Kangals is 72.80 \pm 4.63 cm, and for females, it is 69.20 \pm 4.17 cm.

When it comes to the Akbash, the Turkish white shepherd dog, an officially unrecognized breed, Urošević et al. (2020.) reported that the average height at the withers of males is 66.79 \pm 3.86 cm, and for females, it is 63.15 \pm 3.25 cm. The authors found that the average chest circumference of males is 78.58 \pm 8.19 cm, and for females, it is 77.86 \pm 7.05 cm. In the same population of Akbash dogs, the pastern circumference of males was 13.50 cm \pm 1.87 cm, and for females, it was 13.00 \pm 1.58 cm. It was found that there is no statistical significance in the differences in pastern circumference values.

Materials and Methods

To compare the body structure, or constitution, of four shepherd dog breeds – Tornjak, Akbash, Kangal, and Šarplaninac – we calculated and compared the skeletal strength index and index of robustness.

To calculate the values of the bone and mass indices, it is necessary to measure the dog's height at the withers, the chest circumference, and the pastern circumference. The height at the withers was measured with a Litin stick at the highest point of the dog's body at the withers. The chest circumference was measured with a tape measure behind the elbows, while the pastern circumference was measured with a tape measure at the metacarpal bones. These parameters were measured according to the methodology of Urošević and Drobnjak, 2019. For each breed, 20 males and 20 females were measured. The index of robustness was calculated using the following formula: chest circumference/height at the withers x 100; the skeletal strength index was calculated using the following formula: pastern circumference/height at the withers x 100.

Results

In order to compare the robustness or skeletal strength of the four breeds of shepherd dogs, indexes of robustness and skeletal strength were calculated.

The index of robustness represents the ratio between the chest circumference and the height at the withers. The average value of the robustness index was 124.86 \pm 8.59 in male Tornjaks and 125.22 \pm 9.09 in female Tornjaks. In male Akbash dogs, the robustness index is on average 119.69 \pm 7.51, and in female Akbash dogs, it is 122.75 \pm 7.70. Male Kangals have an average robustness index of 113.91 \pm 5.80, and females have 114.28 \pm 5.41. The average value of the robustness index in male Sarplaninac is 117.48 \pm 6.46, and in females, it is 122.60 \pm 7.77. It is noticeable that in all breeds, females have higher average values of the robustness index than males. In all breeds, both in males and females, the coefficients of variation are very small, ranging from 0.04 to 0.07..

Table 1

	Values of the robustness index by breed							
	Tornjak		Akbash		Kangal		Sarplaninac	
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
Minimum	108.00	98.00	103.00	108.00	97.00	106.00	105.00	106.00
Maximum	148.00	155.00	138.00	140.00	124.00	125.00	133.00	138.00
Mean	124.86	125.22	119.69	122.75	113.91	114.28	117.48	122.60
CV	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.06
SD	8.59	9.09	7.51	7.70	5.80	5.41	6.46	7.77
SE	0.94	0.95	1.21	1.48	0.75	0.71	1.10	1.13

The skeletal strength index represents the ratio of the pastern circumference to the height at the withers. This index reflects the strength and development of the skeleton. The range of variation in the skeletal strength index in Tornjak males is from 18.00 to 26.00, with an average value of 21.40 \pm 1.87 and a coefficient of variation of 0.08. In Tornjak females, the skeletal strength index varies from 17.00 to 25.00, with an average value of 20.90 \pm 1.69. For male Akbash dogs, the average value of the skeletal strength index is 20.10 \pm 1.53, with a range of variation from 17.00 to 23.00. Female Akbash dogs have an average skeletal strength index value

of 20.25 \pm 1.52, with a range of variation from 17.00 to 24.00. In Kangal, this index varies from 19.00 to 26.00 in males and from 19.00 to 25.00 in females. The average value of the skeletal strength index in male Kangal is 22.50 \pm 1.25, and in females, it is 21.94 \pm 1.83. Sarplaninac males have an average skeletal strength index value of 21.67 \pm 1.75, and females have 21.85 \pm 1.80. Of the studied breeds, Kangal had the highest value of this index, followed by Sarplaninac, then Tornjak, and the lowest values were found in Akbash dogs.

Table 2

	Values of the skeletal strength index by breed							
	Tornjak		Akbash		Kangal		Sarplaninac	
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
Minimum	18.00	17.00	17.00	17.00	19.00	19.00	17.00	17.00
Maximum	26.00	25.00	23.00	24.00	26.00	25.00	25.00	26.00
Mean	21.40	20.93	20.10	20.25	22.50	21.94	21.67	21.85
CV	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.08
SD	1.87	1.69	1.53	1.52	1.25	1.83	1.75	1.80
SE	0.20	0.17	0.24	0.29	0.16	0.24	0.30	0.26

Conclusion

For both indexes, very low values of the coefficient of variation (CV) and standard deviation (SD) were determined. This clearly confirms that the observed populations of the four breeds of shepherd dogs are very homogeneous regarding the observed parameters. Differences among breeds, as well as between sexes within breeds, are insignificant. This is completely logical if we consider the necessary biomechanical model of these dogs. Males and females perform the same work in identical terrain, so they require identical strength.

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